

An Overview on The Society, Religion and Social Hierarchy in Early Assam From Historical Perspective

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Abstract

Society is considered as an important institution to organize a group of people. It has a great importance in human civilization since its formation. Historically, society was seen for the first time in human civilization during the neolithic period. From the perspective of sociology, society is a social institution. A well-known sociologist Mac Iver and Page defines society as “the web of social relationship.” There are a number of elements of a society. Religion and social hierarchy are such two important elements. Nowadays, religion and other terms related with it are seen in most of the society of the world. Social hierarchy is also very common in the world like the case of religion. The quantity of sources are small in number that we can use to study about Early Assam. However, Knowledge about the society of Early Assam helps to understand the history of that period from the contemporary perspective. There will be tried to discuss about the society, religion and social hierarchy of Early Assam from historical perspective in this paper.

Keywords: Early Assam, Society, Religion, Caste, Social hierarchy .

Introduction

‘Pre-Ahom Assam’ or ‘Early Assam’ is a construction that is made by the historians on the basis of some features. It refers the period of the history of Assam before the coming of the Ahoms to the Brahmaputra valley. In this term, the historians cover the time range between the fifth and thirteenth centuries A.D. . This main sources to study about this period are literary, epigraphic, numismatic sources and archaeological remains. The large part of these sources cover the epigraphic sources. Nayanjot Lahiri properly mentions in his book ‘Pre-Ahom Assam’, “...these inscriptions, numbering about thirty-two and engraved both on copperplates and stone, constitute the only cohesive body of data for reconstructing the

region's historical past prior to the Ahom invasion in the thirteenth century.”ⁱ In terms of literary sources “the earliest reference to Early Assam as *Kāmrupa* is available in the *Arthasāstra* of Kautilya.”ⁱⁱ The two Indian epics, the *Rāmāyana* and the *Mahābhārata* also give description about early Assam. We can know about this period from Chianese as well as from the archaeological remains like the remains of Dah -Parvatiya. The coins of the contemporary period is also helpful to know about that period.

Methodology

There is used the descriptive methodology to write this paper. This paper is qualitative in nature. Different types of secondary sources are used to write this paper.

Objectives of this paper

The objectives of this paper is to understand about :

- 1) The religious practices in Early Assam.
- 2) The social hierarchy of Early Assam.
- 3) The demographic structure of Early Assam.
- 4) The process of *Aryanisation* in Pre-Ahom Assam.

Society of Early Assam

A society has various elements, viz.— economy, polity, religion, social structure, social hierarchy, food habit, culture etc. . But in this paper, it will be tried to study about the society of early Assam from historical perspective with special reference to religion and social hierarchy of that period.

Religion in Early Assam

Religion is considered as an important and very sensitive element of a society. Different scholars have defined religion from their point own point of view. A well-known sociologist, Emile Durkheim, in his book, ‘The Elementary Forms of Religious Life’ defines religion as “a unified system of beliefs and practices relative to sacred things, that is to says, things set apart and forbidden.”ⁱⁱⁱ In the context of Early Assam, it is seen that religion and religious practices played a significant role in that period also like other part of contemporary India.

Religions practiced in early Assam can be divided into two broad categories :

- 1) Primitive or Tribal Religious Practices
- 2) Aryan or Brahmanical Religion

Primitive or Tribal Religious Practices

There are some arguments among the historian regarding the time of the Aryans’ advent to *Kāmrupā* i.e., Early Assam. However, most of the historians has accepted the fifth century B.C. as the period for the migration of the Aryans as well as the Aryan culture to this land. Before that period, there were the people from other stream of the human population of

the world viz.— the tribes belong to the Proto-Austroloids , the Mongoloid , the Negritos, the Austro- Asiatics, the Tibeto- Burmans etc. in this place. These nom -Aryan people had their own religion and religious practices also. Dr. Banikanta Kakati mentions in his book ‘The Mother Goddess Kāmākhya’, “According to the Kūrana Purāna all the non-Aryan tribes of eastern India were referred to under a group denomination as Kirātas as those of western India as Yavanas.”^{iv} That’s why may be the non-Aryan religious practices in Early Assam is also called as ‘Kirāta Dharma’.

Some elements of this religion are— the worship of phallus or linga, the worship of yoni or female genital organ etc. . It is notable that both are worshipped through some natural objects like stones and trees in a symbolic way. Some other rituals related to the cult of fertility viz.— head-hunting, human sacrifice, ancestor worship and the rites related with dead, magic and sorcery etc. were also practiced by the non-Aryan people of Early Assam. There were some non-Aryan religious practices in Prāgijyotisha-Kāmrupā, which were Hinduized later.

Aryan or Brahmanical Religion

When the Aryan migration started to Early Assam in the time during the 5th century A.D., they brought Aryan culture with them. The Aryans had their own religion and its main scripture was the Vedas. “It consisted the worship of the elements of Nature, but later it developed into personified deities, in midst of which, something like the doctrine of monotheism was worked out with many philosophical ideas.”^v It is not known how and when Brahmanism Aryan religion entered into Early Assam but the historians agree the period 5th-6th century A.D. for the advent of the Aryan religion on the basis of some literary and epigraphic sources. This religion was spread by the patronization of the rulers mainly. Land grant to the Brahmins in the periphery areas of a state and performance of different sacrifices were two main ways to spread this religion. Two important aspects of this religion were *vrata* (fasting) and *dana* (donation/gift). The ‘Aryanization’ or ‘Brahmanisation’ process took place at this land with the expansion of the Aryan religion and culture. As a result of it, many non-Aryan tribal religious beliefs were included in this umbrella-shaped religion. Therefore, some tribal elements are seen in the Brahmanical religion that is practiced in Early Assam. We notice some sects in Brahmanical religion; viz.—1)Shaivism, 2)Saktism, 3)Vaishnavism, 4)Other Religious Practices.

A Brief Description about the Sect of Brahmanical Religion

1)Shaivism:

Shaivism was a popular religious sect from a very early times. This sect refers the sect of Hinduism who worship Shiva as their main deity. This religion was originally a non-Aryan sect but later it was Aryanised. “Rai Bahadur Gunabhiram Boruah states in his *Āsām Burānjī* (1900) that Siva worship was first introduced in early Assam by Jalpeśvara, a king of North Bengal (Jalpaiguri) which was formerly included in the kingdom of Kāmārūpa”^{vi}. It is also mentioned in the Kālikā Purāna that before the rule of Naraka, Shiva was considered as the guardian deity of this region. The same text also “has lists of as many as fifteen sacred places

in Assam associated with the worship of Siva as against five and four connected respectively with Devī and Vishnu.”^{vii} Epigraphic sources also support the popularity of Shaivism in Early Assam, Examples of some of such inscriptions are — the Grant of Vanamāla, the Nidhanpur Grant and the Bargāngā inscription, the Dubi Copperplates of Bhāskaravarman, the Kamauli Copper Plate Grant of Vaidyadeva, etc. . The epigraphic sources of Early Assam refer about Lord Shiva in his various forms. “In the Khanamukh plates of Dharmapāla, it is mentioned that Śiva is the embodiment of both the *śringāra* (erotic) and the *raudrarāsa* (sentiment of Anger)”^{viii}. There is found a myth about Siva in the Gauhati Copperplates of Indrapāla. From the reference mentioned above it can be assumed easily that the worship of Siva was very dominant in Pre-Ahom Assam as Brahmanical deity also.

2) Saktism:

Saktism was also practiced in this region during the period of our discussion. In this cult of Brahmanical religion female goddess is worshipped as the supreme deity. It is believed that this goddess has different appearance in different periods with different names like Devī, Durgā, Parvatī, Kalī, Tāra, Kāmākhya etc.. It has similarity with non-Aryan fertility cult of that period. The concept of ‘Sakti’ is a mixture of various elements like— pre-Aryan, non-Aryan, Aryan and aboriginal. Some Devīs were local in origin and some other were originated in different places, e.g.— Ugratara is originally a Buddhist goddess, Tāra is goddess of Tibetan origin. The female supreme goddess is “considered to be the repository of all energy governing of the universe. In this aspect she is said to preside over creation (*śrishti*), preservation (*sthiti*) and destruction (*samhṛiti*).”^{ix} “The goddess is worshipped in various iconic representations in the form of a *yoni*, symbolizing the creative principle. The procedure of worshipping the goddess is mainly recommended in the *Tantras*. The rituals consist of muttering of *matras* (mystic syllables), drawing of *yantras* (mystic drawing) and application of five makāras (i.e. *Matsya* or fish, *māmsa* or flesh, *madirā* or wine, *mūdrā* or mystic symbols shown in fingers and *maithuna* or sex)”^x. The *Tantras* play an important role in saktism.

Pre-Ahom Assam or Kāmṛūpa was an important centre of saktism. The kāmākhya temple on the Nilāchāla Hill was an important centre of this sect in this region and it is considered as same at present days also. Another noted centre of saktism in pre-Ahom period was the Tamreswari temple at Sadiya. The Devī or the supreme goddess was worshipped in her *kesaikhati* (eater of raw flesh) form in this temple. Kālikā Purana, a prime text of saktism was composed in pre-Ahom Assam to glorify this sect and a list of sacred places related to saktism has also given. Yogini Tantra, another sacred book of saktism was also written in Early Assam. “The Devī Purana, a work composed about the end of the seventh or beginning of the eighth century A.D., states that the Devī was worshipped in her different forms in different places, for instance in Kāmṛupā, Kāmākhya, Bhottadeśa etc.”^{xi}. Wilson mentions about the practice of saktism and Tantricism in Assam or at least the north-east of Bengal (Kāmāṛūpa).

Though Saktism was very popular in Pre-Ahom Assam we have not too many epigraphic reference of it. Only the inscriptions of Vanamāla and Indrapāla to the temples of

Kāmeśvara Mahā-gaurī and Mahā-gaurī Kameśvara . There is a few reference of the existence of saktism in Early Assam in Dubi and Nidhanpur plates of Bhāskarvana also. The tenents and history of Saktism “were preserved in a special class of the mystical and supernatural literature, commonly known as Tantras.”^{xii} . That’s why Tantras are often intertwine .

3)Vaishnavism:

Vaishnavism is that sect of Brahmanical religion who worship Vishnu and his incarnations as the supreme deity. It is hard to say from when the people of the Pre-Ahom Assam started to practice Vaishnavism but we may agree on a point that it was started in this region after 5th century C.E. . It is presume that the Vaishnavism of Early Assam was the pañcarātra type. However, there is no doubt that Vaishnavism was very popular in this region during this period because, the epigraphic sources shows the popularity of the worship of Vishnu. The effort of the rulers’ of Early Assam to trace their descent from Vishnu or his incarnations also proves it. “The first epigraphic reference of Vishnu worship is made in the Badaganga epigraph, where king Bhutivarman is mentioned as *parama-daivata-paramabhagavata*”^{xiii}. But prior to this inscription “the Umāchal Rock Inscription of Surendravarman records the establishment of a cave (temple) dedicated to lord Balabhadra.”^{xiv} It is also an incarnation of Vishnu. Some other epigraphic sources from where the practice and popularity of Vaishnavism in Early Assam can be known are — the Dubi and Nidhanpur plates of Bhaskaravarman, the Hayuñthal plates of Harjara, the Tezpur and Parvatiya plates of Vanamala, the Bargaon plates of Ratnapāla etc. .

The literary sources also refer about the Vaishnavism in Early Assam. “In the Mahābharata Vishnu is called as *Prayjyotisa jyeṣṭha*.”^{xv} The Kālikā Purāna mentions about the worship of five incarnations of Vishnu in this region under the period of our discussion. Some other literary texts such as the *Brahma Purāna*, *Vishnu Purāna* etc. also supports the popularity in Pre-Ahom Assam.

“Archaeological remains and icons of the deity indicate that Vaishnavism prospered fairly well in from the 5th century onwards.”^{xvi}

Other Religious Practices in Early Assam;

Some other religious practices also seen in Early Assam. Tantricism was such a religion. The worship of Sun and some other deities of Brahmanical religion like, *Ganeśa*, *Kārtikeya*, *Indra*, *Brahmā* etc. were also worshipped . A number of sources show that Buddhism (both sects Vajrāyana and Mahāyana) was practiced here.

Social Hierarchy and Caste System in Early Assam

Social hierarchy and caste system are actually a topic of study for sociology. It is equally important to study about it from a historical perspective to understand the social and economic history of a society.

It is well-known that the non-Aryan people had lived in Pre-Ahom Assam since prior to the coming of the Aryans in 5th century C.E. . It is not known whether there was any social

hierarchy or caste system was there before the coming of the Aryans. But after the coming of them, we find the reference of social division or social hierarchy mainly from epigraphic sources of that period. It is notable that in the other parts of India, where the Aryan religion and culture had spread at that time, the population of the society was divided into two broad categories: 1) the Brahmans (the Aryans) and 2) the sudrās (non-Aryans). The same stratification was applied in Pre-Ahom also but, it was applied in a very loose way. That's why we find the '*varṇāśrama-dharma*' (which was the base of social hierarchy of the Aryans) and the term '*varṇa*' (which was another pillar of the *varṇāśrama-dharma*) only in the contemporary inscriptions of this region only. The rulers of Pre-Ahom Assam used the *varṇāśrama-dharma* in the purpose of legitimization and the Brahmanas helped them to do so. We find such kind of reference in this period from the days of the Varman dynasty. The brahmins were donated revenue free land called '*Agraharā*' by the rulers to spread their powers among the people of periphery area of his territory. The brahmins tried to spread their Aryan culture or Aryan social system among the non-Aryan people in their *Agraharas* but the non-Aryan people protested against this effort of them. As the non-Aryan people were large in quantity and the brahmins were minor in number so they compelled to be liberal. Some of the non-Aryan people also accepted the Brahmanical religion but, didn't follow the rules and rituals as strict as the Aryan people. We find the term '*varṇa*' for the first time in the copperplates of Bhāskaravarman. It is known from the epigraphic reference that the Brahmins of Early Assam were exogamic in marital relations and at least some of them observed orthodox rules and duties and sacrifices. There is lack of sources to know about the sudrās or non-Aryan people of that period.

As the *varṇāśrama-dharma* system was loose, so there is not found such strict caste system in Pre-Ahom Assam like the other parts of contemporary India. Instead of Aryan caste system, we notice some professional groups like the *Kāyasthas*, *Keots*, *Kaivarttas*, *KumEbhakaras*, *Tantuvsyas*, *Dandis*, *Daivajnas*, *Ganakas* etc. . The epigraphic sources also support the existence of these professional castes in Early Assam. These professional groups (professional castes) had constituted their own guild and played an important role in administration.

Conclusion

Religion and social hierarchy are two important aspects to understand about the history of a society in a better way. A proper knowledge about the religious practices and social hierarchy of Early Assam is helpful to understand the socio-economic, political as well as cultural history of that period a contemporary period. Yet, the study on socio-cultural aspect of Early Assam have some limitations due to the lack of sources. It is hoped that further research will help to explore more information about the socio-cultural aspects of Early Assam.

Endnotes:

- ii Lahiri, Nayanjot; *Pre-Ahom Assam*, (New Delhi: Munshiram Monoharlal Publishers, 1999), preface vii

- ii Ibid; Introduction,p.11
- ii Durkheim,Emile; *The Elementary of Religious Life*, trans. Karen E. Fields (New York: Free Press,1995),p.44
- ii Kakati, B.K.; *The Mother Goddess Kāmākyā*,(Guwahati: Assam Publication Board,1989),p.9
- ii Choudhury, P.C.; *The History of Civilization of Assam to the Twelfth Century A.D.*(Gauhati: The Department of Historical and Antiquarian Studies of Assam,1959),p.p. 421-422
- ii Barua,B.K.; *A Cultural History of Assam*,vol.: I(Nowgong,Assam: Shri K.K. Barooah,1951),p.143
- ii Barpujari,H.K.(editd.); *Comprehensive History of Assam*,vol.:I(Guwahati: Publication Board Assam,2004),pp.346-347
- ii Lahiri,Nayanjot; op.cit.,p.125
- ii Barpujari,H.K.(editd.);op.cit.,p.366
- ii Barpujari,H.K.(editd.);op.cit.p.317
- ii Barua,B.K.; op.cit.,p.147
- ii Barua,B.K.; op.cit.,p.148
- ii Baruah,S.L.; *A Comprehensive History of Assam*,(New Delhi: Munshiram Manoharlal Publishers,2015),p.161
- ii Barpujari,H.K.;op.cit.p.328
- ii Choudhury,P.C.;op.cit.p.437
- ii Baruah,S.L.; op.cit.,p.p.159-60

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- 8) Sarma, Mukunda Madhava. *Inscriptions of Ancient Assam*. Assam: Department of Publication, Gauhati University,1978. Digital.
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